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Highly advanced modular integration of insulation, energising and storage systems for
non-residential buildings

D9.2 PROMO MATERIAL

WP9 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
WP	Work Package
T	Task
D	Deliverable

1. Publishable summary

Deliverable D9.2 *Promo material* is a public document of the POWERSKIN+ project, issued in the context of WP9 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation, Task T9.1 Communication and Dissemination. A relevant part of the dissemination activities foreseen in the project depends on the production of high-quality dissemination material able to communicate project results and activities to target audiences. For this purpose, a group of initial dissemination tools were developed to support communication and dissemination, in particular: project logo and logo manual, introduction video, roll-up poster, PowerPoint presentation, leaflet and brochure. This document describes the delivered promo materials that has been produced during the first five months of the POWERSKIN+ project.

2. Executive summary

Deliverable D9.2 *Promo material* is a public document of the POWERSKIN+ project, delivered in the context of WP9 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation, Task T9.1 Communication and Dissemination. The objective of task T9.1 is to define a Communication and Dissemination Plan with yearly updates and raise awareness and promotion of project results to potentially interested stakeholders across industry groups, geographical markets, academic community and the wide public.

This document is a follow-up to the already submitted deliverable *D9.1 Project website*, which presented the content and design of the project website in detail. The deliverable D9.2 presents the results of the dissemination activities that were carried on during the first 5 (five) months of the POWERSKIN+ project in order to prepare the project dissemination material. The promotional material designed includes project logo and dedicated manual, introduction video, roll-up poster, project presentation, leaflet and brochure. All the promo materials maintain the same visual identity that was developed as a part of a logo manual and will be updated yearly to reflect the project development. The deliverables D9.1 and D9.2 will serve as tangible documents for delivery of the D9.3 – *Communication and Dissemination plan*.

3. Introduction

A relevant part of the dissemination activities foreseen in the project depends on the production of high-quality dissemination materials able to communicate project results and activities to the target audiences. For this purpose, a group of initial dissemination tools were developed to support communication and dissemination, in particular:

- Project logo and logo manual
- Project introduction video
- Project roll-up poster
- PowerPoint project presentation
- Project leaflet
- Project brochure

This document describes the delivered material that has been produced during the first five months of the POWERSKIN+ project.

4. Project visual identity

Objectives of the project identity are:

- To develop a design structure that would accommodate standard project identity elements, a variable visual identity in various uses, and be able to convey thematic information when needed.
- To allow immediate recognition of the POWERSKIN+ project, thanks to standardized communication templates meant for external audiences.
- To develop specific guidelines and structures related to the project, such as a definite set of colours and/or typography. These guidelines should be applied to templates that are easy to adapt, to understand and to use by the project partners.

4.1 Project logo and logo manual

The initial task for the dissemination material design is logo development. The logo has been created by IPN at proposal stage and was redesigned by FENIX in vector resolution at the beginning of the project (creating a distinguishable project identity). The logo was intended to be simple and recognizable. While designing the logo, it was important that it could reflect the actual branding trends, so that the design is up to date during the whole project lifecycle. It was kept in mind that the target audience should identify the logo at first glance, therefore the logo should be easy to remember, and that it should clearly reflect the aim of the project.

The simplified image of the “building” symbolized by three thick lines is joined by the name of the project situated inside. The chosen typeface is strong and thick to go along with the motive of three thick lines, that represent a building envelope.

For the purpose of the project, two basic versions of the POWERSKIN+ logo were created. The **main logo** is oriented horizontally, and the name of the project is followed by the main motto of the project “walls energizing buildings.”

FIGURE 1 – MAIN PROJECT LOGO

The simplified **square version** will be used on social media and all the graphics with the logo width under 26mm.

FIGURE 2 – SQUARE PROJECT LOGO

The logo uses three colours: orange, black, light grey, and regular white. The POWERSKIN+ logo font is Rubik bold.

FIGURE 3 – PALLET OF COLOURS USED

It is important to follow and respect the project visual identity in order to maximize the impact on the audience. For this reason, a logo manual has been created, outlining the graphical identity guidelines (master brand logo, colour palette, logo usage, logo clear zone, relation to other logos, typography, file formats, applications and errors to avoid).

FIGURE 4 – PROJECT LOGO MANUAL

The Project logo can be used in the following cases:

- in all documents developed under the framework of the POWERSKIN+ project; including documents to be submitted to the EC (e.g. deliverables);
- in project presentations and in dissemination material to be used for communication and dissemination activities carried out by each project participant under the framework of the project;
- on the POWERSKIN+ website, social media and on websites of the project participants with a link to the project website.

The logo is available in both versions on the project website along with the complete logo manual (<https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials>).

5. Dissemination material

In the first 5 months of the project, initial dissemination materials have been designed to support communication and dissemination activities of the POWERSKIN+ project, as part of the task T9.1 Communication and Dissemination. The dissemination material will be updated every twelve months after the project meetings following the project's progression. All dissemination material is available on the project website (www.powerskinplus.eu), and is being regularly shared on the social media profiles (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram) and thematic portals (e.g. BuildUp, EU Agenda, etc.).

5.1 Project introduction video

A short video about the POWERSKIN+ project has been created by the end of the month M2, by FENIX. Since the project is in its early stages, there is still no technical relevant footage available. Therefore, animation has been used to present the project objectives, overall concept, information about demo sites, partners, the project road map and information about the EU funding. The video is available on POWERSKIN+ YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZRKY-My3inc&t=1s> and it has been shared on the European thematic portals – EUAgenda (<https://www.euagenda.eu>) and BUILD UP (<https://www.buildup.eu/>). The video has also been shared on the POWERSKIN+ social media.

FIGURE 5 – PROJECT INTRODUCTION VIDEO

5.2 Project roll-up poster

The one-page roll-up poster (format 85x200cm) has been designed for the POWERSKIN+ project by the end of month one (M1), by FENIX. Project partners have already been attending relevant meetings and expos, so they have used the roll up design in their stands and booths and they have been already spreading awareness about the project. The roll-up poster includes the project’s main motto, general objectives of the project, the website and social media links, partners’ logos and the statement of financial support from the European Union. The poster is available on the project website (<https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials>) and has been shared on social media.

FIGURE 6 – PROJECT ROLL-UP POSTER

5.3 PowerPoint presentation

The project presentation in PowerPoint has been designed for the POWERSKIN+ project by the end of month 3 (M3), by FENIX. The project presentation includes general information of the project, concept, objectives, a timeline of the project and information about demonstration sites. Furthermore, contact information, website link, social media links, partners and the statement of financial support from the European Union is also present. The presentation is available on the project website (<https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials>) and it has also been shared on the POWERSKIN+ social media.

FIGURE 7 – PROJECT POWERPOINT PRESENTATION

5.4 Project leaflet

The project leaflet has been designed by the end of month one (M1), by FENIX. The format is A5 (210 x 148 mm) and it contains essential information about the project – the overall concept, partners, website and social media link. Further details about POWERSKIN+ can be found in a follow-up promo material – the project brochure (see below). The leaflet is available on the project website (<https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials>) and has been shared on social media.

FIGURE 8 – PROJECT LEAFLET

5.5 Project brochure

In addition to the project leaflet that contains only essential information about the POWERSKIN+ project, FENIX has designed in month three (M3) a project brochure. The format is the same as the leaflet (A5 - 210 x 148 mm), but it contains more information and the page count is doubled compared to the leaflet. Apart from the overall concept and partners that were presented already in the leaflet, the brochure provides additional information about the project concept, objectives and demonstration sites. Furthermore, the brochure provides all social media links and a QR code. The brochure is available on the project website and has been shared on social media (<https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials>).

FIGURE 9 – PROJECT BROCHURE

6. Conclusion

All dissemination materials generated are in accordance with the visual identity of POWERSKIN+ project. It has been designed and created with the intention of updating it every twelve months following the project progress. The material listed above is available to the public on the project website and has already been shared on the social media and used during the dissemination events. Some of the material (i.e. leaflet, introduction video) has also been posted on the thematic portals (BUILD UP, EUAgenda) in order to get more reach of the project content to the target audiences as well as to get more traffic to the project website and social media profiles.

